

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH ENGLISH MOVIES

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Abstract: This article is about teaching English through movie. In this article it is spoken about the role of teaching English through movies and several successful reasons of using it at the English lessons.

Key words: movie, atmosphere, learning, skills, motivate, imagination, material, improves.

Аннотация: Эта статья посвящена обучению английскому языку с помощью кино. В этой статье говорится о роли обучения английскому языку с помощью фильмов и нескольких успешных причинах его использования на уроках английского языка.

Ключевые слова: фильм, атмосфера, обучение, навыки, мотивации, воображение, материал, совершенствуется.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz tilini kino orqali o'rgatish haqida bo'lib, unda ingliz tilini filmlar orqali o'rgatishning o'rni va ingliz tili darslarida undan foydalanishning bir qancha muvaffaqiyatli sabablari haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: kino, atmosfera, o'rganish, ko'nikmalar motivatsiya, tasavvur, material, takomillashtirish.

The purpose of teaching English is to develop the four language skills of reading, listening, speaking, and writing, Because it is not easy to get students interested in improving the four skills of the language, English teachers should plan the lesson as much as possible. Teaching English should be active, innovative, creative, educational, and fun.

In order to teach and improve teaching quality; a wide variety of teaching methods should be used in the classroom. English teachers are required to be innovative now

not handiest in the usage of learning methods or techniques, but also in the use of teaching aids. A movie or film is one of the instructional media that can be used by English teachers to improve student's English skills.

Films may be a pleasing and motivating device for students. Using movies has brought authenticity, variety; reality, and flexibility into classrooms. Movies allow students to enjoy information in real-life language.

There are many advantages of using English movies in the classroom. First, the students enjoyed the assigned activities in the classroom. Movies make students interested in seeing and hearing real-life situations. They were influenced by the fact that films provided a favorable ecosystem.

Second, movies can improve better for English teachers to play English movies with English subtitles. English films with subtitles have a significant positive effect on students' listening skills compared to films without subtitles.

Third, movies can improve students' English speaking ability, especially fluency. Students can watch movies in English and then talk about them. Fourth, when the film is shown with English subtitles, students can see first-hand how words are written, and by watching English films, students will notice many new phrases and expressions, mainly idioms and colloquial expressions. Students can hold a word with them and write down any new words or phrases that catch their attention. They can show up later or ask their English teachers. Students can record new words or phrases they hear in their notebooks. They can later look up words they don't understand or ask their English teachers.

Aside from so many advantages, the use of English movies in the classroom still has disadvantages or problems.

First, watching movies takes a long time, and as a result, students get bored. Using English movies in the classroom will reduce student's time to do classroom activities such as writing or having discussions.

Second, students in films focus on the appearance of the actors or actresses, and as a result, they deviate from the main educational goal and focus more on the actors.

Third, movies can force students to imitate actors or actresses' horror scenes. There are several scary scenes from English movies that are usually imitated by students, including action scenes, adult scenes, smoking scenes, etc.

To overcome the side effects of the film, English teachers should consider the following solutions.

First, teachers should use short English movies to save time in learning. Second, teachers should always remind their students of the main learning objective before and after watching the film. English teachers can also pause movies and remind students about exercises when they don't understand.

Third, thinking, imagination, and emotional.

Fourth, instructors need to pick out a good instructional English movie. Fourth, instructors need to pick out a good instructional English movie.

To overcome the bad effects of films, English teachers must keep in mind a few answers which includes teachers have to use brief English film to save time in gaining knowledge of, instructors have to continually remind students the main instructional goal before and after watching the movies, teachers should control student's thinking, imagination, and emotional, and teachers should select a good educational English movies.

REFERENCES

1. Champoux, J.E. & Robert, O.A.(2007). Film as a teaching resource. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 8(2), 240-251.
2. Kalean, I. (2013). Speaking skill improvement by using movie as media. *Educational Journal of Islamic University of Malang*,13(1), 155-160
3. Mirvan. X. (2013). The advantages of reading skills in the EFL classroom. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 13(4), 62-67.
4. Pratiwi, M.R. (2010). Improving pronunciation ability using English cartoon films.